

LEGAL BASIS OF ISLAND SEA PROTECTION AND ITS IMPROVEMENT - THE NEED OF THE TIME

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ANNOTATION

In this article, the legal basis of the protection of the Aral Sea and the need for its improvement, international cooperation in this regard, measures to solve the problems of the Aral Sea are highlighted based on analytical opinions.

KEY WORDS: Island protection, international cooperation, ecological situation, irrigation,

The drying up of the Aral Sea, international organizations, environmental problems, the world community. The aggravation of the ecological situation on the island and its shores worries the world community. The Aral Strait is one of the largest regional ecological disasters, and more than 35 million people living in the sea basin, including a large part of the population of Uzbekistan, live under its influence. In the recent past, the Aral Sea, considered one of the largest lakes in the world, is rapidly drying up. The main reason for the drying up of the Aral Sea is the sharp decrease in flow as a result of the use of Amudarya and Syrdarya waters for irrigation. The increase in the area of irrigated land in Central Asia and the improper use of water have decided the fate of the Aral Sea. In the last 40-45 years, the sea level has dropped by 22 meters (53 m in 1961) and the volume of water has decreased from 1064 km³ to 80 km³, in its place there have been shoals and shifting sands. At the end of 2010, it was noted that the sea level was at an absolute height of 24 meters. As a result, 45,000 km² of it dried up and turned into dry land. The long-term average seawater salinity is 9-10 g/liter, but now it has increased to 110-280 g/liter, and the sea has lost its importance as a bioproductive basin. Biodiversity has declined dramatically. The number of 174 animal species in the marine region has decreased to 40.

The drying up of the Aral Sea has led to the aggravation of the socio-ecological situation in the Aral Bay region. Every year, 15-75 million tons of salt and dust rises from the dry bottom of the island, causing air and soil pollution in a very large area. Natural and anthropogenic desertification is increasing on the island coast. The amount of salts in drinking water is 2-4 g/l, and water

consumption in some regions does not exceed 5 l (norm-200-300 l). Morbidity and death rates among the population have reached high levels.

There are no options left to restore the Aral Sea to its original state. It is impossible to maintain the level of the Aral Sea under the current conditions. It is of great importance to create artificial forests in the dry place of the island to take measures against the blowing of sand and salt by the wind. Since 1981, in the dry part of the sea, trees and shrubs: white and black saxovol, kandim, churkez and other plants have been cultivated, which gave good results, and now 25 thousand hectares of forests are being created every year. The newly opened sea floor is covered with salt and plants may not grow at all.

The countries of Central Asia are working together to solve the problems of the island and the islands. The United States, Japan, Germany, France and other developed countries, the United Nations, the World Bank and various state and non-state international organizations are contributing to the positive solution of the institution of this century. The Aral Sea and the Aral Bay region are administratively located in the territory of Uzbekistan and Kazakhstan. includes the desert. In the recent past, its area, including the islands, was almost 68,000 square meters. km. of water volume is 1000 cubic km. established The average depth is 50.5 m. was around. 38.6 cubic km from Amudarya to the Aral Sea until the 60s of the 20th century. 14.5 cubic km from Syrdarya. water comes, 5.5 cubic km. underground water was also added. The shipping season in the sea with large ports such as Aralsk and Moynok lasted for 7 months. The island problem is considered to be one of the biggest disasters of the 21st century in terms of environmental, socio-economic consequences. Taking into account the fact that this problem is universal, Uzbekistan initiated the creation of the UN special commission on the island and the holding of an international conference on this problem under the leadership of the UN. In 1993, the first President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Islam Karimov, spoke at the 48th session of the UN General Assembly and drew the attention of the world community to the tragedy of the Aral Sea. Our President emphasized that the Arol problem is a global problem not only of Uzbekistan or Central Asia, but of the whole world. In addition, on October 24, 1995, the head of our state at a special meeting of the General Assembly on the occasion of the fiftieth anniversary of the establishment of the United Nations, the ecological tragedy related to the drying up of the Aral Sea, the biosphere covering the entire earth, the living conditions, health and offspring of tens of millions of people he emphasized that it is a problem with a devastating effect, and emphasized that it cannot be solved

without the organizational activities of international organizations, including the UN. Uzbekistan is boldly moving towards ensuring human rights and freedoms based on equal cooperation with the world community, forming a socially and ecologically oriented market economy, establishing a democratic legal state and a free civil society.

During the years of independence, our country has accumulated enough experience in eliminating environmental problems and their negative consequences. Since the first days of independence, large-scale work has been carried out to eliminate environmental problems, prevent their negative consequences, and protect the environment and human health. For information, it should be said that in 2008, our country hosted the international conference on "Island problems, their impact on the population gene pool, flora and fauna, and measures of international cooperation to alleviate their consequences." Within the framework of this event, which was held with the support of the UN, the Program for 2011-2015 on providing assistance to the countries of the Aral Sea basin was developed, in which more than 300 projects worth 8.5 billion It was decided to transfer funds in excess of US dollars. It's not for nothing, of course. Because the island was once recognized as the 4th largest island in the world. The unique sea and its surroundings were an incomparable natural world, a place of beautiful biodiversity. At that time, the island was literally considered a source of life between two deserts...

Consequently, Uzbekistan has been constantly drawing the attention of the world community to this urgent issue from prestigious international platforms. At the 48th session of the UN General Assembly on September 28, 1993, this acute problem was raised by the head of our country for the first time, and at the 50th session of this organization on October 24, 1995, under the auspices of the UN Environment Program, the Aral Sea and the Aral Bay the initiative to organize a council on the problems of yi was put forward. Mobilizing the funds of international associations to take the necessary measures for the implementation of programs and projects aimed at improving the socio-economic and ecological conditions in the Aral Sea basin, as well as international cooperation on reducing the tragic consequences of environmental destruction in the future. aimed at development. The United Nations General Assembly adopted a special resolution on the Aral Bay region. About 60 countries from different regions of the world participated in this resolution as co-authors. In it, the General Assembly announced its support for regional activities and initiatives aimed at improving the environmental, social, economic and

demographic situation in the Aral Bay region. The General Assembly calls on all stakeholders to conduct joint interdisciplinary research, develop and deploy environmentally friendly technologies, promote inclusive and environmentally sustainable economic growth and use of energy and water efficient technologies. Aralboyi became the first region to be awarded such a high status as "Territory of Ecological Innovations and Technologies" by the General Assembly, reports say. The document serves to summarize the practical actions and projects of specialized agencies, funds and programs in the UN system to support regional priority, integration and sustainable development and to ensure coordination between them.

Shavkat Mirziyoyev first announced the initiative to grant the status of the region of ecological innovation and technology to the Arolbay region in August 2018 at the meeting of the founding countries of the International Fund for Island Rescue. This decision of the President, with the joint efforts of the countries of the region, attracts investments in the development and introduction of environmentally friendly, energy and water-saving technologies, collective application of the principles of "green economy", prevention of desertification and ecological migration processes, development of ecotourism and other measures he emphasized that it will help to create the necessary conditions for the implementation of events.

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